

Uploading and linking research data/software at GSI

v. 4.1

June 2024

Document Updates:

v2.2 Description on the request correction button to send an email to the library to add the linking Dataset/Software/Article

v.2.3 Includes technical instructions on linking. Updates on how to treat software versioning in the GSI repository. Clarification on software abstract in Zenodo. Citations in GitHub repo

v.2.4 Small Errors Corrected

v.3.0 Additional section added on publishing research software now includes example from GSI GitLab

v.3.1 Added link to GSI/FAIR RDM policy. Added information on ESCAPE OSSR and Helmholtz Research software directory

v4 Included information on Embargo periods and allowing access. Updated instructions and screenshots to reflect changes in Zenodo UI

v4.1 Update OSSR link

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1 Introduction

For questions, comments, or required assistance please contact the open science team open-science@gsi.de (note: support only available for users of the GSI and FAIR facilities).

A dedicated webpage to [Open Science at GSI/FAIR](#) is available for more information.

The [GSI/FAIR policy on research data management](#) and the [GSI/FAIR Open source software licence Guidelines](#) are available online.

This document details how to publish research data and software to an external repository, create records in the GSI publications repository (<https://repository.gsi.de/>), and link them to the corresponding publication record. Publishing research data and software is crucial for compliance with the GSI Research Data Management Policy, and for the Helmholtz POF4 indicators. To learn more about Open Science at GSI and GSI's open access policy please visit:

<https://www.gsi.de/work/forschung/open-science>

https://www.gsi.de/en/work/research/ethics_rules

As a first step, please refer to the flowchart below for guidance on how to identify a suitable research data repository. When publishing research data, the goal is to include items that can replicate the results and findings, and make the data as interoperable and reusable as possible. If the data you wish to publish is too large, consider using a smaller subset of data, such as result data from plots which can still prove useful.

2 Publishing Data to Zenodo

The publication repository Zenodo is hosted by CERN in collaboration with [OpenAIRE](#), and can provide up to 50GB of data storage per record (more is available upon request). In addition, a persistent identifier for the data record in the form of a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) is allocated, which can then be linked to the GSI publications repository in the method described in [section 4](#) below.

Please note that each new DOI generates costs, and thus please use with consideration. If you wish to test Zenodo, there is a Sandbox version which generates dummy DOIs: <https://sandbox.zenodo.org/>

The detailed user manual for uploading data to Zenodo can be found here <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5603317>

- a. Go to <https://zenodo.org/> and login or sign up. This would preferably be done using the ORCID account.

- a. Once logged in, click on the button in the top right of the menu bar and select 'New Upload'. This loads a form where record metadata about the data can be entered.

- b. Start by selecting which files to publish (if applicable). Also upload any readme documentation or additional data/metadata description files. Note that the data cannot be changed once the record is published, however, it can be saved for future

modifications before publishing.

The screenshot shows the Zenodo interface during the 'before publishing' stage. At the top, there's a navigation bar with the Zenodo logo, a search bar, and links for 'Communities' and 'My dashboard'. Below this is a header for the current record, 'a.k.mistry...'. The main content area is divided into two sections: a 'Files' section on the left and a 'Draft' management sidebar on the right.

Files Section:

Preview	Filename	Size	Progress
<input type="checkbox"/>	TestResultData1.ascii md5: 11e0a8d55f3d12690fae54be7515	2.41 KB	100%
<input type="checkbox"/>	TestResultData1.csv md5: 45c70b6d2e64aa32c113531449a1ee9	1.25 KB	100%
<input type="checkbox"/>	TestResultData2.ascii md5: 84b427a63f73197e2c32601c7abec32	1.31 KB	100%
<input type="checkbox"/>	TestResultData2.csv md5: f582c5da3b6f1192ee4a0f701c1670	1.36 KB	100%
<input type="checkbox"/>	DatasetMetadata.json md5: cbe296d71c90a340e688c5a74351c2	7.46 KB	100%
<input type="checkbox"/>	DatasetMetadata.xml md5: e1666bacf326a0909aa1742e85c9f5e	6.82 KB	100%

Storage available: 6 out of 100 files, 20.60 KB out of 50.00 GB

Drag and drop files - or - Upload files

Draft Management Sidebar:

- Buttons: Save draft, Preview, Publish
- Visibility: Public (selected), Restricted
- Public status: The record and files are publicly accessible.
- Options: Apply an embargo (Record or file protection must be restricted to apply an embargo).

‘Basic information’ section

c. Leave the ‘Digital Object Identifier’ field blank, as a DOI will automatically be assigned. **You can ‘reserve’ the DOI in advance, such that this can be provided to the journal article for linking to the dataset pre-publication.**

The screenshot shows the 'Basic information' section of the Zenodo interface. It features a blue header with the text 'Basic information'. Below this, there is a section for the 'Digital Object Identifier' (DOI) with the following elements:

- A label: **Digital Object Identifier ***
- A question: 'Do you already have a DOI for this upload?' with radio buttons for 'Yes' and 'No' (selected).
- A text input field: 'Copy/paste your existing DOI here'.
- A button: 'Get a DOI now!' (highlighted with a red box).

d. Scroll down to ‘Resource type’ and select ‘Dataset’ from the drop-down list. Fill out the ‘Title’ and ‘Creators’ fields. The authors(creators) may not necessarily have to be those in the published journal article, but could be the person responsible for publishing the data, the principal investigator, and/or the data analysts for example.

Resource type *
Dataset

Title *
GSI Test Dataset

+ Add titles

Publication date *
2024-05-21

In case your upload was already published elsewhere, please use the date of the first publication. Format: YYYY-MM-DD, YYYY-MM, or YYYY. For intervals use DATE/DATE, e.g. 1939/1945.

Creators *

Mistry, Andrew Kishor Data manager

+ Add creator

Remove Edit

e. In the ‘Description’ field, describe the data set in as much detail as possible.

Description

Paragraph

Here, the dataset should be described in as much detail as possible. Metadata and other data structure should be given. If needed, a separate document describing the dataset in advanced detail can be uploaded.

The code used to process this data can be found here: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8413374>

The data was part of experiment XYZ, collected in the period 24.12.2021 - 05.01.22 at GSI Helmholtzzentrum für Schwerionenforschung GmbH, with experiment number G-22-00123

The experimental instrument used was the DESPEC setup coupled to the SHIP separator

This is a randomly generated test dataset for the purposes of providing documentation for publishing data to Zenodo, and linking to the GSI publications repository. It in no way represents any real scientific data, and should only be used for test purposes.

The dataset is in the form of Result Data in a table three columns of Energy in electronvolts (eV), counts and etc. etc.

The data is given in the format of both .csv and .ascii. Software ABC can be used to open and access the files.

f. The default **license** is Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International. This is an open access license and is recommended for data publication at GSI, unless there are data protection or technology transfer considerations. This information can be edited here.

Licenses

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International
The Creative Commons Attribution license allows re-distribution and re-use of a licensed work on the condition that the creator is appropriately credited. [Read more](#)

Edit Remove

+ Add standard + Add custom

A note on licenses: According to the research data management policy of GSI/FAIR, the open access license should be Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC-BY 4.0). <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>

Recommended information section

g. The important information to include here are the version number (this can be entered as desired) and the Publisher information. An example is given for data generated at GSI.

▼
 Recommended information

Contributors

+ Add contributor

Keywords and subjects

Suggest from: All ▼ Search for a subject by name ▼

Languages

Search for a language by name (e.g "eng", "fr" or "Polish") ▼

Dates

Format: DATE or DATE/DATE where DATE is YYYY or YYYY-MM or YYYY-MM-DD.

+ Add date

Version

1.0

Mostly relevant for software and dataset uploads. A semantic version string is preferred see semver.org, but any version string is accepted.

Publisher

GSI Helmholtzzentrum für Schwerionenforschung GmbH

The publisher is used to formulate the citation, so consider the prominence of the role.

Funding Section

h. Include any Grants. You can search for an existing award in the system or add a new one.

▼
 Funding

Awards

☰ Decay Studies of Exotic Heavy Nuclei with RISING at the GSI Fragment Separator EPID0036281 Edit Remove

+ Add award + Add custom

Related Works section

- i. Add linked references, such as the software code used to generate results from the dataset, the journal article, and the instrument.

Related works
▼

Specify identifiers of related works. Supported identifiers include DOI, Handle, ARK, PURL, ISSN, ISBN, PubMed ID, PubMed Central ID, ADS Bibliographic Code, arXiv, Life Science Identifiers (LSID), EAN-13, ISTC, URNs, and URLs.

Related works

Relation *	Identifier *	Scheme *	Resource type		
Is supplemented by ✕	.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.7871129	DOI ✕	Software	✕	✕
Is cited by ✕	/10.1016/j.nuclphysa.2019.05.003	DOI ✕	Publication / Journal article	✕	✕
References ✕	doi.org/10.15120/GSI-2024-00534	DOI ✕	Physical object	✕	✕

+
Add related work

- j. The remainder of the sections (Software, Publishing information, Conference) can be ignored.

Visibility Section

- k. The right side of the form shows the visibility of the files once published. At this point, public (open access) can be selected.
- l. After **previewing** the record as a check, Click **'Save draft'** and then **'Publish'**. The record is now available and accessible with the DOI.

Draft ⓘ

Save draft Preview

Publish

Visibility *

Files only

Public Restricted

Public
The record and files are publicly accessible.

Alternatively, embargo periods may be applied, for instance, when a data/software metadata record needs to be created before the publication of a journal article, while simultaneously restricting full access to the data files.

m. The DOI for data/software can be generated in advance, such that it can be directly entered into the publication data and software availability sections. Access to these data files may be provided to specific individuals, such as the article reviewers (explained below).

Visibility *

Files only

Public Restricted

The files of this record are restricted.

Embargoed (files-only)
The record is publicly accessible. On 31 August 2024 the files will automatically be made publicly accessible. Until then, the files can only be accessed by users specified in the permissions.

Options

Apply an embargo ⓘ
Record or files protection must be restricted to apply an embargo.

Embargo until *

2024-08-31
Format: YYYY-MM-DD

Embargo reason

Data files will be made open access after article publication

*After **'Publishing'** the record, it is now available and can be viewed.*

n. The record can be modified if needed, but note that uploading additional data files will require an iteration of the version number, and a new DOI will be generated. **'New version'** can be selected to update the record as needed (new DOI will be generated).

o. The record files can be made public at any time using the **'Edit'** button and changing the visibility to **'Public'**

p. If the record files are restricted through an embargo, you may only wish to allow access to certain people (e.g. reviewers). This can be done by selecting **'Share'** and subsequently generating a new link. The link can also be set with an expiration date, or can be manually deleted at any time.

Edit
New version
Share

Share access

Links Access requests

Link title	Created	Expires	Access	
-	0 seconds ago	Never	<div style="border: 1px solid #ccc; padding: 5px;"> Can view Can view restricted records/files. Can preview Can view drafts and restricted records/files. Can edit Can edit drafts and view restricted records/files. </div>	Delete Copy link

Create a new link

Short name for your link (optional). Expiration date: YYYY-MM-DD or never if blank (optional).

Close

3 Publishing software on Zenodo

Ensure that the group leader (and Principal investigator) has agreed to publication of the software, and that appropriate measures have been taken to ensure good software development practices.

Publishing software on Zenodo generates a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) for the software version that is then accessible. Note that it is recommended to use the GSI Gitlab for software developments. If GitHub is used, this can be done automatically through Zenodo. If the software is on GSI Gitlab (<https://git.gsi.de/explore/projects>) then proceed to step [3.2](#)

To ensure proper tracking and preservation of modified code, utilise version control, or establish a separate repository for the code. Obtain a unique DOI for this new version, and add a record for this versioning/repository in the GSI publications repository (see section [4](#)).

Please note that each new DOI generates costs, and thus please use with consideration. If you wish to test Zenodo, there is a Sandbox version which generates dummy DOIs: <https://sandbox.zenodo.org/>

The detailed user manual for uploading data to Zenodo can be found here <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5603317>

Scientific software can be onboarded to the Open-source Scientific Software Repository (OSSR), which enables curation and cross-community sharing. Please see here for more details <https://purl.org/escape/ossr>

The software may also be added to the Helmholtz Research Software directory. <https://helmholtz.software/>

For questions or comments on the OSSR or Helmholtz repositories, please contact open-science@gsi.de and we will link you to the respective on-site experts.

3.1 Publishing on Zenodo via GitHub

An example is given of some basic test software uploaded to GitHub. The GitHub repository has to be public for this to work. Please ensure that your code has been checked/curated by another party before publishing.

a. Login to Zenodo (either create an account or preferably use ORCID), and select GitHub from the menu

b. **Connect** to your GitHub account

c. Toggle the code repository you wish to publish to **'On'**

d. Back in GitHub, a **release** has to be made for the software. Please follow the GitHub guide on releases if you are unsure: [GitHub release instructions](#)

After a release is made, a DOI is automatically generated and a zipped version of the released code is automatically uploaded to Zenodo. Please note, initially this may take 10-15 minutes.

e. You can view the releases by clicking on the link in the **'Enabled Repositories'** section

Repositories > **amist88/GSI_SoftwarePublishTest** ON

Releases Create release

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.11234839](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11234839)

- Zenodov2 **amist88/GSI_SoftwarePublishTest: Release 2** ✓ Published
 DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.8413374](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8413374) 7 months ago
[Release 2](#)
- Zenodov3 **amist88/GSI_SoftwarePublishTest: Release 3** ✓ Published
 DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.11234839](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11234839) 27 seconds ago
[Release 3](#)

f. This will take you to the record page. You can 'Edit' the record at this time to add more information

zenodo Search records... Communities My dashboard a.k.mistry...

There is a newer version of the record available.

Published October 6, 2023 | Version Zenodov2 Software Open **Edit** New version Share

amist88/GSI_SoftwarePublishTest: Release 2

Andrew Mistry

Show affiliations

GSI_SoftwarePublishTest: Release 2

#Here, the code and any associated metadata should be explained as best as possible.

This is a test example for trial purposes.

The data was part of experiment XYZ, collected in the period 24.12.2021 - 05.01.22 at GSI Helmholtzzentrum für Schwerionenforschung GmbH, with experiment number G-22-00123 The experimental instrument used was the DESPEC setup coupled to the SHIP separator.

None of this represents any real scientific data or analysis, and should only be used for test purposes.

The two codes are for randomly generated datasets which can be found here: Result Datasets <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7274417>

The codes extracts data from the .csv data files, cleans the dataset, and perform a very basic Gaussian fit. Software_TestResultData1.ipynb can be used with TestResultData1.csv Software_TestResultData2.ipynb can be used with TestResultData2.csv

The codes can be used with JupyterLab, or Jupyter Notebook, which is available in a webbrowser without the need to install any software locally. <https://jupyter.org/try>

Files

amist88/GSI_SoftwarePublishTest-Zenodov2.zip		
amist88/GSI_SoftwarePublishTest-Zenodov2.zip		
amist88-GSI_SoftwarePublishTest-6cc4262		
README.md	1.0 kB	
Software_TestResultData1.ipynb	29.6 kB	
Software_TestResultData2.ipynb	29.3 kB	

Name	Size	Download all
amist88/GSI_SoftwarePublishTest-Zenodov2.zip	43.0 kB	Preview Download

Details

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.8413374](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8413374)

Resource type: Software

Publisher: Zenodo

Views 17 **Downloads** 0

[Show more details](#)

Versions

Version Zenodov3	May 21, 2024
Version Zenodov2	Oct 6, 2023

[View all 2 versions](#)

Cite all versions? You can cite all versions by using the DOI 10.5281/zenodo.8413373. This DOI represents all versions, and will always resolve to the latest one. [Read more.](#)

External resources

Indexed in [OpenAIRE](#)

Communities

This record is not included in any communities yet.

Basic Information

g. Most of the fields should be already populated but amendments can be made as needed. Details including the README file text can be pasted into the ‘**Description**’ box.

h. Authors can be added as ‘**Creators**’ as needed.

Basic information ▼

Digital Object Identifier *

Do you already have a DOI for this upload? Yes No

10.5281/zenodo.8413374 ✕

Reserve a DOI by pressing the button (so it can be included in files prior to upload). The DOI is registered when your upload is published.

Resource type *

Software ▼

Title *

amist88/GSI_SoftwarePublishTest: Release 2

+ Add titles

Publication date *

2023-10-06

In case your upload was already published elsewhere, please use the date of the first publication. Format: YYYY-MM-DD, YYYY-MM, or YYYY. For intervals use DATE/DATE, e.g. 1939/1945.

Creators *

+ Add creator

Andrew Mistry (GSI Helmholtzzentrum für Schwerionenforschung GmbH) Remove Edit

Description

Paragraph B I

GSI_SoftwarePublishTest: Release 2

#Here, the code and any associated metadata should be explained as best as possible.

This is a test example for trial purposes.

The data was part of experiment XYZ, collected in the period 24.12.2021 - 05.01.22 at GSI Helmholtzzentrum für Schwerionenforschung GmbH, with experiment number G-22-00123 The experimental instrument used was the DESPEC setup coupled to the SHIP separator.

None of this represents any real scientific data or analysis, and should only be used for test purposes.

The two codes are for randomly generated datasets which can be found here: Result Datasets <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7274417>

The codes extracts data from the .csv data files, cleans the dataset, and perform a very basic Gaussian fit. Software_TestResultData1.ipynb can be used with TestResultData1.csv Software_TestResultData2.ipynb can be used with TestResultData2.csv

The codes can be used with JupyterLab, or Jupyter Notebook, which is available in a webbrowser without the need to install any software locally. <https://jupyter.org/try>

- i. The next step is to define the license. The default GSI software license is GPLv3 (GNU General Public License version 3), however **please consult the GSI policy on open software licenses** found on [here](#). Consider if the software contains any Technology Transfer aspects, third party software etc. that must be taken into account.

Licenses

GNU General Public License v3.0 or later
 Permissions of this strong copyleft license are conditioned on making available complete source code of licensed works and modifications, which include larger works using a licensed work, under the same license. Copyright and license notices must be preserved. Contributors provide an express gran... [Read more](#)

Edit Remove

+ Add standard + Add custom

Recommended information section

- j. In particular ensure the versioning is consistent with the release and the publisher is correct.

Recommended information ▼

Contributors

+ Add contributor

Keywords and subjects

Suggest from All Search for a subject by name

Languages

Search for a language by name (e.g "eng", "fr" or "Polish")

Dates

Format: DATE or DATE/DATE where DATE is YYYY or YYYY-MM or YYYY-MM-DD.

+ Add date

Version

Mostly relevant for software and dataset uploads. A semantic version string is preferred see [semver.org](#), but any version string is accepted.

Publisher

The publisher is used to formulate the citation, so consider the prominence of the role.

- k. In **related works**, links to the dataset, journal article, instrument etc. (for example) can be added

Related works
▼

Specify identifiers of related works. Supported identifiers include DOI, Handle, ARK, PURL, ISSN, ISBN, PubMed ID, PubMed Central ID, ADS Bibliographic Code, arXiv, Life Science Identifiers (LSID), EAN-13, ISTC, URNs, and URLs.

Related works

Relation *	Identifier *	Scheme *	Resource type
Is supplemented by ✕	https://github.com/amist88/GSI_Sr	URL ✕	Software ✕
Is cited by ✕	10.5281/zenodo.7274417	DOI ✕	Dataset ✕

+
Add related work

- l. It is not strictly necessary to include information to the **‘Software’** and **‘Publishing information’**, and **‘Conference’** sections. A link to the GitHub project is automatically included in the release. However for completeness on the repository status and programming language you may wish to fill this out.

Software
▼

Repository URL

https://github.com/amist88/GSI_SoftwarePublishTest

URL or link where the code repository is hosted.

Programming language

Python ✕

Repository's programming language.

Development Status

Active ✕

Repository current status.

Visibility Section

- m. The right side of the form shows the visibility of the files once published. At this point, public (open access) can be selected.

- n. After **previewing** the record as a check, Click **‘Save draft’** and then **‘Publish’**. The record is now available and accessible with the DOI.

Alternatively, embargo periods may be applied, for instance, when a data/software metadata record needs to be created before the publication of a journal article, while simultaneously restricting full access to the data files.

- o. The DOI for data/software can be generated in advance, such that it can be directly entered into the publication data and software availability sections. Access to these data files may be provided to specific individuals, such as the article reviewers (explained below).

After ‘Publishing’ the record, it is now available and can be viewed.

- p. The record can be modified if needed but note that additional files will require an iteration of the version number, and a new DOI will be generated. ‘New version can be selected to update the record as needed (new DOI will be generated).

q. The record files can be made public at any time using the **'Edit'** button and changing the visibility to **'Public'**

r. If the record files are restricted, you may only wish to allow access to certain people (e.g. reviewers). This can be done by selecting **'Share'** and subsequently generating a new link. The link can also be set with an expiration date, or can be manually deleted at any time.

Optional: After publication, you can add a citation file for the published work to your GitHub repository. Please see the documentation: [Citing work in GitHub](#)

3.2 Publishing on Zenodo via GSI GitLab

If you publish via GSI Gitlab (<https://git.gsi.de/explore/projects>) follow the above steps. Please ensure that your code has been checked/curated by another party before publishing.

- a. In the GSI GitLab, go to the project page and download the project as a compressed file (Code-> Download source code)

- b. In Zenodo go to new upload

- c. Upload the compressed project file

Basic Information Section

d. You can ‘reserve’ the DOI in advance, such that this can be provided to the journal article for linking to the software pre-publication.

Basic information

Digital Object Identifier *

Do you already have a DOI for this upload? Yes No

e. Scroll down to ‘Resource type’ and select ‘Software’ from the drop-down list. Fill out the ‘Title’ and ‘Creators’ fields. The authors(creators) may not necessarily have to be those in the published journal article, but could be the person responsible for publishing the software, the principal investigator, and/or the software developer for example.

Resource type *

Software

Title *

GSI_TestSoftware_RDM-main

Publication date *

2024-05-21

In case your upload was already published elsewhere, please use the date of the first publication. Format: YYYY-MM-DD, YYYY-MM, or YYYY. For intervals use DATE/DATE, e.g. 1939/1945.

Creators *

Andrew Kishor, Mistry (GSI Helmholtz Centre for Heavy Ion Research) Data manager

Creators *

Andrew Kishor, Mistry (GSI Helmholtz Centre for Heavy Ion Research) Data manager Remove Edit

Creators *

Andrew Kishor, Mistry (GSI Helmholtz Centre for Heavy Ion Research) Data manager

f. Add details about the code to in the Description field. If necessary, copy and paste the README file from the code repository here.

Description

Paragraph

GSI_TestSoftware_RDM

#Here, the code and any associated metadata should be explained as best as possible.

This is a test example for trial purposes.

The data was part of experiment XYZ, collected in the period 24.12.2021 - 05.01.22 at GSI Helmholtzzentrum für Schwerionenforschung GmbH, with experiment number G-22-00123 The experimental instrument used was the DESPEC setup coupled to the SHIP separator.

None of this represents any real scientific data or analysis, and should only be used for test purposes.

The two codes are for randomly generated datasets which can be found here: Result Datasets <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7274418>

The codes extracts data from the .csv data files, cleans the dataset, and perform a very basic Gaussian fit. Software_TestResultData1.ipynb can be used with TestResultData1.csv Software_TestResultData2.ipynb can be used with TestResultData2.csv

The codes can be used with JupyterLab, or Jupyter Notebook, which is available in a webbrowser without the need to install any software locally. <https://jupyter.org/tr/>

g. Define the license. The default is set to Creative Commons, so use 'Edit' to change it to an appropriate software license. A full list of software licenses can be found on the *Change Standard License* pop up. The *Recommended* tab has a list of common licenses.

The default GSI software license is GPLv3 (GNU General Public License version 3), however **please consult the GSI policy on open software licenses** found on [here](#). Consider if the software contains any Technology Transfer aspects, third party software etc. that must be taken into account.

Licenses

GNU General Public License v3.0 or later
 Permissions of this strong copyleft license are conditioned on making available complete source code of licensed works and modifications, which include larger works using a licensed work, under the same license. Copyright and license notices must be preserved. Contributors provide an express grant of patent rights. [Read more](#)

Change standard license

Search

- Apache License 2.0**
 A permissive license whose main conditions require preservation of copyright and license notices. Contributors provide an express grant of patent rights. Licensed works, modifications, and larger works may be distributed under different terms and without source code.
- Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International**
 The Creative Commons Attribution license allows re-distribution and re-use of a licensed work on the condition that the creator is appropriately credited.
- Creative Commons Attribution Share Alike 4.0 International**
 Permits almost any use subject to providing credit and license notice. Frequently used for media assets and educational materials. The most common license for Open Access scientific publications. Not recommended for software.
- Creative Commons Zero v1.0 Universal**
 CC0 waives copyright interest in a work you've created and dedicates it to the world-wide public domain. Use CC0 to opt out of copyright entirely and ensure your work has the widest reach.
- GNU General Public License v3.0 or later**
 Permissions of this strong copyleft license are conditioned on making available complete source code of licensed works and modifications, which include larger works using a licensed work, under the same license. Copyright and license notices must be preserved. Contributors provide an express grant of patent rights.
- MIT License**
 A short and simple permissive license with conditions only requiring preservation of copyright and license notices. Licensed works, modifications, and larger works may be distributed under different terms and without source code.

Recommended information section

h. In particular ensure the versioning is consistent with the release and the publisher is correct.

▼
 Recommended information

Contributors

+ Add contributor

Keywords and subjects

Suggest from: All Search for a subject by name

Languages

Search for a language by name (e.g "eng", "fr" or "Polish")

Dates

Format: DATE or DATE/DATE where DATE is YYYY or YYYY-MM or YYYY-MM-DD.

+ Add date

Version

2.0

Mostly relevant for software and dataset uploads. A semantic version string is preferred see semver.org, but any version string is accepted.

Publisher

Zenodo

The publisher is used to formulate the citation, so consider the prominence of the role.

i. In **related works**, links to the dataset, journal article, instrument etc. (for example) can be added

▼
 Related works

Specify identifiers of related works. Supported identifiers include DOI, Handle, ARK, PURL, ISSN, ISBN, PubMed ID, PubMed Central ID, ADS Bibliographic Code, arXiv, Life Science Identifiers (LSID), EAN-13, ISTC, URNs, and URLs.

Related works

Relation *	Identifier *	Scheme *	Resource type
Is supplemented by ✕	<input type="text" value="https://github.com/amist88/GSI_Sr"/>	URL ✕	Software ✕
Is cited by ✕	<input type="text" value="10.5281/zenodo.7274417"/>	DOI ✕	Dataset ✕

+ Add related work

j. Include Repository and code information to the **‘Software’** section.

Software
▼

🔗 Repository URL

URL or link where the code repository is hosted.

🔗 Programming language

Python
✕

Repository's programming language.

💖 Development Status

Active
✕

Repository current status.

Visibility Section

k. The right side of the form shows the visibility of the files once published. At this point, public (open access) can be selected.

l. After **previewing** the record as a check, click **‘Save draft’** and then **‘Publish’**. The record is now available and accessible with the DOI.

Draft ℹ

📄
Save draft

👁
Preview

📄
Publish

🛡 Visibility*

Files only

Public

Restricted

🔓

Public

The record and files are publicly accessible.

Alternatively, **embargo periods** may be applied, for instance, when a data/software metadata record needs to be created before the publication of a journal article, while simultaneously restricting full access to the files.

m. The DOI for data/software can be generated in advance, such that it can be directly entered into the publication data and software availability sections. Access to these data files may be provided to specific individuals, such as the article reviewers (explained below).

24

The screenshot shows a 'Visibility' section with a toggle for 'Files only' set to 'Restricted'. Below this, a message states 'The files of this record are restricted.' An 'Embargoed (files-only)' section explains that the record is publicly accessible but files are restricted until 31 August 2024. The 'Options' section includes a checked 'Apply an embargo' checkbox, an 'Embargo until' date field set to '2024-08-31', and an 'Embargo reason' text area containing 'Data files will be made open access after article publication'.

After ‘Publishing’ the record, it is now available and can be viewed.

- n. The record can be modified if needed but note that additional files will require an iteration of the version number, and a new DOI will be generated. ‘New version can be selected to update the record as needed (new DOI will be generated).
- o. The record files can be made public at any time using the ‘**Edit**’ button and changing the visibility to ‘**Public**’.
- p. If the record files are restricted, you may only wish to allow access to certain people (e.g. reviewers). This can be done by selecting ‘**Share**’ and subsequently generating a new link. The link can also be set with an expiration date, or can be manually deleted at any time.

4 Linking entries between publication and research data/software in the GSI repository

This example focusses on Zenodo, but applies to any item published with a DOI (or other persistent identifier) in an external repository. The workflow for journal/data/software is given here:

The instructions on how to execute the workflow are given in the following. If help is needed with any of the steps, please contact the open science team (open-science@gsi.de) (note: support only available for users of the GSI/FAIR Facility)

a. In the GSI repository (<https://repository.gsi.de/>), first **create the record of the journal article/written publication**. A description of how to do this can be found here: <https://join2.de/Main/GSItipps>

b. Next is to create a record for the dataset. Select "SUBMIT".

GSI REPOSITORY

SEARCH **SUBMIT** PERSONALIZE ▼ HELP ADMINISTRATION ▼

Search 174,470 records for:

any field

[Search Tips](#)

GSI's portal to the references of the scientific publications and to the open access full texts

[Recent additions to publications database](#)

GSI Scientific Reports
[2021](#), [2020](#), [2019](#), [2018](#), [2017](#), [2016](#), [2015](#), [2014](#), [2013](#), [2012](#), [2011](#), [2010](#), [2009](#), [2008](#), [2007](#), [2006](#), [2005](#), [200](#), [1988](#), [1987](#), [1986](#), [1985](#), [1984](#), [1983](#), [1982](#), [1981](#), [1980](#), [1979](#), [1981/82](#), [1979/80](#), [1977](#), [1976](#)

GSI Short Reports
[2020](#), [2019](#)

GSI FUE Programs
[2020](#), [2019](#)

Narrow by collection:

- Publications database** (16,432)
- Open Access** (3,389)

c. Scroll down to "Other Resources" and select "Dataset". This will load the submission form

- Other Resources
 - Abstract
 - Communication
 - **Dataset**
 - Event
 - Form / Template
 - Internal Report
 - Multimedia
 - Minutes
 - News
 - Notes
 - Physical Object
 - Preprint
 - Project
 - Software
 - Website

d. Go to the external repository and copy the Digital Object Identifier (DOI): example here is given of a test dataset in Zenodo.

zenodo Search Upload Communities a.k.mistry@gsi.de

November 2, 2022 Dataset Closed Access Edit

GSI Test Dataset

Andrew Kishor Mistry

Here, the dataset should be described in as much detail as possible. Metadata and other data structure should be given. If needed, a separate document describing the dataset in advanced detail can be uploaded.

The data was part of experiment XYZ, collected in the period 24.12.2021 - 05.01.22 at GSI Helmholtzzentrum für Schwerionenforschung GmbH, with experiment number G-22-00123

The experimental instrument used was the DESPEC setup coupled to the SHIP separator

This is a randomly generated test dataset for the purposes of providing documentation for publishing data to Zenodo, and linking to the GSI publications repository.

The dataset is in the form of Result Data in a table three columns of Energy in electronvolts (eV), counts and etc. etc.

The data is given in the format of both .csv and .ascii. Software ABC can be used to open and access the files.

Sample 1	Energy	Counts	Time
	eV	eV ⁻¹	S
	0	9	26.8
	1	4	29
	2	6	27.8
	3	1	33.2
	4	4	29.4

Indexed in OpenAIRE

Publication date: November 2, 2022

DOI: **10.5281/zenodo.7274418**

Keyword(s): Nuclear Physics, Research Data Management

Versions

- e. In the GSI repository submission form, copy the DOI (e.g. 10.5281/zenodo.7274418) into the 'Import data' field and press enter. The fields should load into the form.

Submit New Record

Dataset Submission

Import data Import history Use the IMPORT field above to import from bibliographic resources or other records. Your imports will show up here

- f. Please fill in the remaining fields (e.g. POF4, Department, ensure relevant for VDB is selected etc.)

g. Make sure to edit the primary author and select them as 'corresponding author from the drop down list

h. If the record of a publication is available in the GSI repository please enter this information into the 'Additional information/General Notes' field.

The journal publication record is shown here with its recordID

i. At the bottom of the page, click the **“Finish & Release”** button.

j. *If you plan to also publish the software, omit this step until the software record has been entered.* Open the newly created record and at the bottom of the page click **‘Request correction’**. An email link should appear where you can specify that you wish the linking between dataset/software and article which will inform the library department to do this step.

Only after the document has been cross-checked by the editors (RDM officer/library) does the record become public, and only then are linking and data searches available (in the meantime they remain restricted and the full link cannot be seen).

k. When entering the software record in the GSI publications repository, please do the same as for the dataset record. In this case, **please provide the RecordID for the journal record (internal GSI record) in the ‘Additional information/general notes’ field, and in addition the RecordID for the dataset record (if applicable).** Then select **‘Request correction’** at the bottom of the record page. This is to notify the Library and documentation department that this should be linked back to the journal article record.

In the additional information field, the journal article ID is given.

In summary, if you have a journal article, a dataset and software that is published externally, In the GSI publications repository:

- 1. Create a journal article record and note the journal recordID.**
- 2. Create a Dataset record and import the external dataset repository record via the DOI (e.g. in Zenodo). Then, write the journal recordID into the 'Additional information/General Notes' field**
- 3. Create a Software record. Again, link to the external repository with the DOI (e.g. in Zenodo). Write the journal recordID AND the dataset recordID (if applicable) into the 'Additional information/General Notes' field**
- 4. Go to any of the records and click 'Request correction' at the bottom of the page. In the email that appears, state that the records should be linked**

The remaining steps to link the software record to the journal article record and vice versa will be completed by the RDM coordinator/library and documentation department.

The example below shows a completed record with dataset and software linked after the library and documentation department, or RDM coordinator has completed the final linking steps.

Information | Files | Holdings

0028-0836
Journal Article GSI-2022-00011

GSI Test Journal Article for Research Data Management

Mistry, A. K. (Corresponding author)*
2022
Nature Publ. Group London [u.a.]

Nature <London> 605, 1 (2022) ○○○

Abstract: This is a test record to describe how to link research data from an external repository to the GSI publications repository

Classification:

- ddc:500

Contributing Institute(s):

1. Bibliothek & Dokumentation (BUD)

Research Program(s):

1. 612 - Cosmic Matter in the Laboratory (POF4-612), (POF4-612)

Experiment(s):

1. (Altdata therefore no facility)

Database coverage:
PubMed[®]; BIOSIS Previews; Biological Abstracts; Chemical Reactions; Clarivate Analytics Master Journal List; Current Contents - Agriculture, Biology and Environmental Sciences; Current Contents - Life Sciences; Current Contents - Physical, Chemical and Earth Sciences; Ebsco Academic Search; Essential Science

Indicators: IF >= 40; Index Chemicus; JCR; Nationallizenz² gefördert von der ; SCOPUS; Science Citation Index Expanded; Web of Science Core Collection; Zoological Record

The record appears in these collections:
Private Institute collections > >WGF > >RED > BUD
Document types > Articles > Journal Article
Infrastructure > Library & Documentation
Workflow collections > Public records
Publications database

Linked articles:

Software
Mistry, A. K. (Corresponding author)*
[amist88/GSI_TestSoftware_RDM: GSI Test Code Release 1](#)
[10.5281/ZENODO.7277784]

Dataset
Mistry, A. K. (Corresponding author)*
[GSI Test Dataset for Research Data Management](#)
[10.5281/ZENODO.7274418]

[BibTeX](#) | [EndNote XML](#) | [Text](#) | [RIS](#)

[BibTeX](#) | [EndNote XML](#) | [Text](#) | [RIS](#)

Record created 2022-11-02, last modified 2022-11-03 [Similar records](#)

If modifications are needed, this can be done with the "Modify this record" button in the lower right corner of the record view, as long as the entry has not yet been processed in the workflow. If you still need to make changes then please use the "Request correction" link in the lower right corner of the detailed record view. An email will automatically be sent to gsilibrary@gsi.de

5 Useful Links

GSI Ethics and Rules Link: https://www.gsi.de/en/work/research/ethics_rules

GSI/FAIR Open Science Webpage: <https://www.gsi.de/work/forschung/open-science>

GSI repository: <https://repository.gsi.de/>

GSI repository Wiki Guide: <https://join2.de/Main/GSIHelpAndTipps>

Zenodo <https://zenodo.org/>

Zenodo user guide: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5603317>

Zenodo Sandbox (for testing purposes) <https://sandbox.zenodo.org/>

GitHub release project notes: <https://docs.GitHub.com/en/repositories/releasing-projects-on-GitHub/managing-releases-in-a-repository>

Creative Commons licenses: <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>

6 Additional technical notes for maintainers

Linking to digital research objects such as manuscripts, datasets, software, and instruments. This is done by entering justlink:[record ID] or justlink:[DOI] in the import field (via Modify Record). Although a single record can have multiple links, you can only enter one link per record. Therefore, to link a single record (A) to multiple others (B, and C), you should enter the linking information through records B, C.

To link three objects A, B and C; in record A use justlink:B and so on as shown in the diagram below:

When there is more than one dataset to link to a given journal record, use justlink on both dataset records to the journal article (note: software cannot be linked in this case to dataset record D).

Below is the record of A after following the above A, B, C, D workflow.

Information Files Holdings
● 2041-1723

Journal Article GSI-2023-00005

A. Journal Record

[Mistry, A. K.](#) (Corresponding author)*
 2023
 Nature Publishing Group UK [London]

[Nature Communications](#) 1(1), 1 (2023) ● ○ ○

Abstract: Explanation on justlink connections in JOIN2 Repo

Classification:

- [ddc:500](#)

Contributing Institute(s):

1. [Bibliothek & Dokumentation \(BUD\)](#)

Research Program(s):

1. [623 - Data Management and Analysis \(POF4-623\)](#) (POF4-623)

Database coverage:

DIRECTORY OF OPEN ACCESS JOURNALS ; Article Processing Charges ; BIOSIS Previews ; Biological Abstracts ; Clarivate Analytics Master Journal List ; Current Contents - Agriculture, Biology and Environmental Sciences ; Current Contents - Life Sciences ; Current Contents - Physical, Chemical and Earth Sciences ; DOAJ Seal ; Essential Science Indicators ; Fees ; IF >= 10 ; JCR ; PubMed Central ; SCOPUS ; Science Citation Index Expanded ; Web of Science Core Collection ; Zoological Record

The record appears in these collections:

- Private Institute collections > >WGF > >RED > BUD
- Document types > Articles > Journal Article
- Infrastructure > Library & Documentation
- Workflow collections > Public records
- Publications database

Linked articles:

Dataset
[Mistry, A. K.](#) (Corresponding author)*
C. Dataset Record [BioRx](#) | [Environ](#) | [XMAS](#) | [Tad](#) | [NIS](#)

Dataset
[Mistry, A. K.](#) (Corresponding author)*
D. Dataset Record [BioRx](#) | [Environ](#) | [XMAS](#) | [Tad](#) | [NIS](#)

Software
[Mistry, A. K.](#) (Corresponding author)*
B. Software Record [BioRx](#) | [Environ](#) | [XMAS](#) | [Tad](#) | [NIS](#)

Record created 2023-02-15, last modified 2023-02-15 [Similar records](#)